

T.C.
HATAY MUSTAFA KEMAL UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NATURAL & APPLIED SCIENCE

**VARIABILITY and CHANGE of HUMIDEX and ABSOLUTE HUMIDITY
on the COASTS of TÜRKİYE**

Vural ENGÜL

**DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS and REMOTE
SENSING**

MASTER'S THESIS

HATAY
FEBRUARY - 2024

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ABSTRACT

VARIABILITY and CHANGE of HUMIDEX and ABSOLUTE HUMIDITY on the COASTS of TÜRKİYE

Air Temperature and relative humidity are the primary variables that determine the thermal comfort of living organisms. The presence of humidity in the air has effects on the perceived temperature, and on hot summer days with high humidity, the temperature feels higher than what the thermometer measures. The concept of humidex was introduced to explain the impact of humidity on perceived temperature. Humidex is particularly significant in coastal areas where humidity can be high, affecting thermal comfort and human health. As the air temperature increases, both the amount of evaporation and the amount of humidity the air can hold also increase.

Türkiye is a topographically high and rugged country consisting of two peninsulas, Anatolia and Thrace. A significant portion of the country's population resides along the coasts. Additionally, tourism activities in coastal areas are more intense during the summer months compared to other seasons. Türkiye is considered among the high-risk countries for the adverse effects of climate change, especially since it is located in the Eastern Mediterranean Basin where the impacts of climate change are expected to be intense.

The aim of this study is to identify the regions on the coasts of Türkiye where humidex increases and decreases during the summer months, and thus investigate the evolution of the comfort level of coastal residents and the impact of humidex fluctuations on living comfort. In the study, areas where humidex increases and decreases on the coasts of Türkiye are identified, and these trends are visualized, determining the direction of future changes in humidex. Relative humidity and air temperature data obtained from stations operated by the Turkish State Meteorological Service (MGM) in 61 different settlements along the coastal regions of Türkiye are used for calculating humidex. These data consist of hourly measurements taken in June, July, and August. Humidex and absolute humidity are calculated using hourly relative humidity and air temperature data, and absolute humidity analysis is conducted to understand the cause of trends in humidex. The variability and changes in humidex (perceived temperature with humidity) from 1990 to 2022 are analyzed using the Mann-Kendall test, Sen's trend slope method, correlation analysis, and regression analysis.

The outputs obtained from the analysis of the variability and changes in humidex in coastal areas with high population and tourism density will serve as a reference for measures to be taken for both human health and thermal comfort. The study results will provide a projection for urban planning, tourism, and cooling systems.

In all 61 stations examined on the coasts of Türkiye, the air temperature has increased. In 90% of these 61 stations, it has been determined that humidex has increased at least twice the rate of air temperature. The increase in air temperature has increased evaporation and the air's capacity to carry humidity in all locations.

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Key Words: Humidex, Apparent temperature, Relative humidity, Absolute humidity, Mann-Kendall test

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LIST of SYMBOLS and ABBREVIATIONS

SYMBOLS

°C	: Derece Celsius
°K	: Derece Kelvin
J	: Joule
N	: Newton
m	: Metre
Pa	: Pascal
g	: gram
kg	: kilogram

ABBREVIATIONS

HX	: Humidex (°C)
RH	: Relative humidity (%)
AH	: Absolute humidity (g/m ³)
NSC	: No significant trend at 95% confidence interval
r	: Correlation coefficient
T	: Temperature
T _d	: Dew point temperature
e	: Water vapor pressure
e _s	: Saturated water vapor pressure
<i>m</i>	: Mass (kg)
<i>V</i>	: Volume (m ³)
IPCC	: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
netCDF	: Network Common Data Form
MGM	: Turkish State Meteorological Service
DMİ	: General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works
MMCC	: Maximum moisture carrying capacity

1. INTRODUCTION

Although the interaction of every living being with climate and their sensitivity to it varies, climate plays a significant role in both the existence and extinction of organisms as well as their health and comfort (Shivanna, 2022). Climate is crucial for human thermal comfort and health as it affects human production, distribution, and consumption processes. It is evident that humans will be affected much more by climate change both biologically and in terms of their activities (Haines et al., 2004). Even in regions where the climate does not change much, people are affected by daily and seasonal variations throughout their lives. People's clothing preferences, socio-cultural lives, and production activities are also influenced by these changes.

In recent years, the impact of climate change on living organisms has become increasingly important and subject to research. Variables changing in climate emerge as criteria for the thermal comfort and health of organisms, especially humans (Schweiker et al., 2018). Apart from its complex structure and inclusion of many meteorological variables, climate has a characteristic of causing unexpected outcomes even with small changes (Bryson, 1974). For example, small changes occurring in meteorological variables activate positive or negative feedback mechanisms, leading to different outcomes than expected (Webb et al., 2006).

Air temperature ranks among the primary meteorological variables in climate. Air temperature is a crucial climatic element not only because of its influence on other variables but also due to its impact on thermal comfort and human health. However, air temperature provides only partial information regarding the thermal comfort and health of organisms. For instance, on hot summer days with high humidity between June and August, the perceived temperature is higher than the temperature measured by the thermometer. This is because the regulation of body temperature involves a cooling mechanism through the evaporation of sweat on the skin (Kalkan, 2018).

As the humidity in the air increases, sweat on the human skin evaporates more slowly and over a longer period, thus slowing down the body's cooling function through evaporation. Consequently, on days with high temperature and humidity, people feel more uncomfortable and uneasy compared to dry days with the same temperature. It is

concluded that thermal comfort decreases on days with both high temperature and humidity (Gagnon et al., 2018).

Due to the relationship between temperature, relative humidity, and the sweating-evaporation-cooling mechanism in the body, a variable called humidex has been developed by the Canadian Meteorological Service (Santee et al., 2005). Humidex is the temperature perceived by a human due to the combined effect of temperature and relative humidity (Masterson et al., 1979). This variable, also known as perceived temperature in Turkish, is used in this study with its original name "humidex."

The most significant factor affecting thermal comfort, following the trend of increasing humidex values, is global temperature change. Global temperatures have increased significantly from the pre-industrial era to 2021, by about 1.1–1.2°C. The average global temperature over the past five years is almost the highest recorded. In the last 45 years, land temperatures have increased about twice as fast as ocean temperatures (Simmons et al., 2021).

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published the first part of its sixth assessment report (AR6) on August 9, 2021, summarizing the findings of climate science that will guide policy in the years to come. The full AR6 report represents a significant scientific endeavor that evaluates the physical science basis for climate change and synthesizes findings from over 14,000 peer-reviewed publications. The purpose of this informational document is to provide a concise summary of the following key scientific messages (Ming et al., 2021):

1. Human activities are causing climate change. This impact leads to more frequent extreme events such as heatwaves, intense rainfall, and droughts, as well as ongoing sea-level rise.
2. We now have more precise estimates of the climate system's sensitivity to carbon dioxide emissions, allowing for better assessment of the potential outcomes of emission increases or reductions.
3. Even in the most aggressive emission reduction scenario, the world will continue to warm until at least 2050.
4. Carbon dioxide is the primary contributor to atmospheric warming. Each ton of carbon dioxide emitted contributes to planetary warming.

5. There is still time to avoid dangerous climate change, and the effects of emission reductions will begin to be felt within the next decade.

Future temperature projections from each scenario are derived from a wide range of climate models. These models have higher resolution than those used in previous IPCC reports. All scenarios predict global warming to reach 1.5°C by 2050 without significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. Without a substantial decrease in emissions, it is estimated that global surface temperatures will increase by at least 2.1°C by 2100 compared to 1850-1900 levels. Keeping temperatures within 2.5°C above pre-industrial levels represents a geological time period tens of thousands of years ago.

The report emphasizes the average of all models reaching a certain level of warming (e.g., 2°C) to assess the environmental impacts. It states that in all warming scenarios, land surface temperatures will increase more than ocean surface temperatures.

The IPCC's latest report, the "AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023," published on March 20, 2023, provides a comprehensive overview of climate change. It includes the latest findings on the causes, impacts, and mitigation of climate change, along with summarizing the policy implications. The report highlights the highly likely conclusion that human influence has been the main driver of observed warming since the mid-20th century. It also emphasizes that the effects of global warming are already significant and expected to intensify in the future. While opportunities still exist to limit climate change, the report notes that these opportunities are diminishing and calls for urgent action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to the impacts of climate change (IPCC, 2023).

Some key findings of the AR6 Synthesis Report include:

- Without substantial reductions in carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gas emissions in the next decade, global warming of 1.5°C and 2°C will be exceeded in the 21st century.
- Limiting global warming to 1.5°C will require rapid, far-reaching, and unprecedented changes across all sectors of society.
- Even if global warming is limited to 1.5°C, significant climate impacts such as more extreme weather events, sea-level rise, and changes in agricultural yields will still occur.

- The impacts of climate change will be most severe for the world's poorest and most vulnerable people.
- While there is still time to limit climate change, the window of opportunity is beginning to close.

The AR6 Synthesis Report serves as a clear warning about the consequences of climate change. Urgent action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to its impacts is essential (IPCC, 2023).

According to the IPCC's AR6 Synthesis Report, if current emission trends continue, global temperatures could exceed 1.5°C by 2030. This will lead to more severe impacts of climate change (IPCC, 2023). The effect of climate change on sea surface temperatures, melting glaciers, increased evaporation leading to higher humidity, undoubtedly indicates an increase in humidex values. When combined with ongoing temperature increases, the heightened humidity will inevitably pose a threat to life. From this perspective, analyzing humidex trends along the coasts of Türkiye aims to draw conclusions about the trajectory and rates of changes.

Located between the 36°-42° north parallels and 26°-45° east meridians, Türkiye appears as a peninsula extending east to west. Despite having coastlines on the Mediterranean, Aegean Region, Marmara Region, and Black Seas, its elevation and the orientation of mountains result in a structure where maritime influences are limited in the inland areas (see Figure 1.1). Factors such as the orientation and elevation of mountains contribute to the diversity of the country's climate. Nevertheless, the country generally falls within the Mediterranean macro-climate region.

Türkiye is located in the Eastern Mediterranean Basin, where the effects of climate change are expected to be particularly intense. Therefore, Türkiye is considered among the high-risk countries in terms of the adverse effects of climate change (Silkin, 2014). Consequently, there is a need for studies on monitoring climate, variability in climate, and adaptation to mitigate the negative impacts of climate change (MGM3, 2015).

Due to its geographical location as a peninsula, Türkiye has more population in coastal provinces compared to inland provinces (Demir, 2018). The convergence of land, water, and air ecosystems in coastal areas, along with the natural environment and various types of land use potential, increases the population in coastal areas. With its favorable climate conditions, fertile soils, water resources, and suitable morphological features,

Türkiye's coastal areas possess rich potential for human and economic activities. This has led to the concentration of human and economic activities, especially settlement, agriculture, tourism, transportation, trade, and industry, in coastal areas. Coastal areas have become focal points for population and economic activities in our country. Climate is one of the main factors contributing to the high population density in coastal areas, and it is also an important factor in the distribution of population (Kocadağlı, 2022).

In Türkiye, tourism activities are generally concentrated along the coastal strip, depending on geographical and climatic conditions. The density in coastal tourism increases in summer due to climatic conditions. The primary factors determining the duration of the tourism season, especially in sea-sun-beach tourism, are air temperatures and sea water temperatures. Since human health is adversely affected by relative humidity above 70% (Kum et al., 2018), the amount of humidity in the air also affects the course of tourism activities along with temperature. Humidity, temperature, and wind factors are the key determinants of thermal comfort; therefore, tracking these parameters' average values, trends, and extreme values are crucial in climate assessments.

Along with the population density on the coasts of Türkiye, transportation, tourism, and other economic activities are also carried out intensively. As stated in the IPCC 6th assessment report, global air temperatures are rising and will continue to rise, so it is important to determine the changes and trends in humidex, which is a measure of thermal comfort and human health, on the coasts of Türkiye. Simply detecting changes in air temperature alone will not reflect the clear impact on human health and comfort. Therefore, in this study, long-term changes and trend analyses in parameters such as temperature, humidex, absolute humidity, and relative humidity on the coasts of Türkiye have been conducted.

Weather stations with suitable meteorological data for the study were selected from the settlements located on the coasts of Türkiye. Care has been taken to include all of Türkiye's coasts in the study (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1. The locations of the 61 stations referenced in the study

1.1. Purpose of the Study

This study aims to examine the variability and changes in humidex during the summer months between 1990 and 2022 along the coastlines of Türkiye, with the objective of identifying regions where humidex has increased or decreased. Consequently, the study seeks to reveal the comfort levels and fluctuations in comfort experienced by coastal residents. Furthermore, trends in the increase or decrease of humidex in regions where such changes occur along the Turkish coastlines will be identified, and the direction of future changes in humidex will be evaluated. Care has been taken to gather data from at least 10 different stations from each geographical region along the coast of Türkiye for the study. Samples were specifically selected from stations where trends of increase or decrease in humidex and absolute humidity, along with other parameters, were highly pronounced and analyzed in detail. The outputs obtained from the analysis of the variability and changes in humidex in coastal areas with high population, settlement, and tourism density will serve as a reference for measures to be taken for both human health and thermal comfort.

1.2. General Climate Characteristics of the Turkish Coastlines

Türkiye is located between the temperate zone and the subtropical zone. The geographical features of Türkiye, being surrounded by seas on three sides and the presence of mountains affecting the inland areas, have led to the emergence of various climate types. Coastal regions of our country exhibit milder climate characteristics due to the influence of the seas. The Northern Anatolian Mountains and the Taurus Mountains prevent the penetration of maritime influences into the inland areas (Figure 1.2.a; Figure 1.2.b). Therefore, continental climate characteristics are observed in the inland regions of our country. Inland and eastern regions experience high temperature amplitude values due to continental effects, while average temperatures remain low. Conversely, temperature averages are higher especially along the western and southern coasts. Additionally, in recent years, the regions where temperature increase during the warm period is most pronounced are the Black Sea and Mediterranean regions. Particularly noteworthy is the temperature increase at stations in the Eastern Mediterranean, western part of Southeastern Anatolia, Eastern Black Sea, Thrace, and the southern part of the Aegean Region (Erlat and Güler, 2018). In terms of precipitation, rainfall values in coastal areas are higher compared to inland areas where continental conditions prevail (Figure 1.3; Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.2. a) Türkiye DEM (Digital Elevation Model). b) Climate Zones (Atalay, 1997)

Based on the criteria used in global climate classifications, the following climate types can be distinguished along the coasts of our country (Atalay et al., 1997):

- Mediterranean Climate
- Marmara Region (transitional) Climate
- Black Sea Climate

Figure 1.3. Türkiye long-term (1991-2020) average temperature map (MGM2, 2023)

Figure 1.4. Türkiye long years (1991-2020) areal rainfall normals (MGM1, 2023)

1.1.1. Mediterranean Climate

This climate prevails over a significant portion of the Aegean Region and the western part of Inner Anatolia, where elevation and continental influences diminish, as well as on the southern slopes of the Taurus Mountains facing the Mediterranean, and along the coastal strip in this region. The Mediterranean climate is characterized by hot and dry summers, and mild and rainy winters. The number of days

with snowfall and freezing events is very limited along the coastal areas close to the sea. As one moves towards higher altitudes in this climate, winters become snowy and colder. In the true Mediterranean climate, the average temperature in January is 6.4°C, while the average temperature in July, the hottest month, is around 26.8°C, with an annual average temperature of approximately 16.3°C (Figure 1.5). There are settlements where these values hover around 19-20°C. In the Mediterranean Region, the average annual total precipitation is 665.1 mm (Figure 1.6), with the majority of rainfall occurring during the winter season. Since the share of summer rainfall in the annual total is 5.7%, it can be stated that summer drought prevails in the region. The annual average relative humidity is 63.2%. Annual precipitation values and average temperatures along the Aegean Region coast are relatively lower compared to the Mediterranean coast (Figure 1.7; Figure 1.8) (Sensoy et al., 2005).

Figure 1.5. Mediterranean Region Average Temperatures (MGM2, 2023)

Figure 1.6. Precipitation distribution by years in the Mediterranean Region (MGM1, 2023)

Figure 1.7. Aegean Region Average Temperatures (MGM2, 2023)

Figure 1.8. Precipitation distribution by years in the Aegean Region (MGM1, 2023)

1.1.2. Marmara Region (Geçiş) İklimi

Marmara Region Bölgesi'nin kuzey Aegean Region'yi de içine alacak Figurede güney kesiminde yaşanan iklim koşullarıdır. Marmara Region iklimi, karasal Black Sea Region ve Mediterranean Region iklimleri arasında bir geçiş özelliği göstermektedir. Kışları Mediterranean Region ikliminden biraz daha soğuk, yazları Black Sea Region ikliminden daha az yağışlıdır. Kışlar karasal iklim kadar soğuk olmamakla birlikte, yazları karasal iklimden daha yağışlıdır. Soğuk ay olan ocak ayı ortalama sıcaklığı 4.9 °C, sıcak ay olan temmuz ayı ortalama sıcaklığı 23.7°C, yıllık ortalama sıcaklık 14.0°C'dir (Figure 1.9). Ortalama yıllık toplam yağış 670 mm'dir (Figure 1.10) ve yağışların çoğu kış mevsiminde düşmektedir. Yaz yağışlarının yıllık toplam içindeki payı %11.7'dir. Yıllık ortalama nispi nem %73'tür (Atalay ve ark., 1997).

Figure 1.9. Average Temperatures in Marmara Region Region (MGM2, 2023)

Figure 1.10. Precipitation distribution by years in Marmara Region Region (MGM1, 2023)

1.1.3. Black Sea Region İklimi

This climate type is influential in the coastal and north-facing mountainous areas of the Black Sea Region and the Black Sea coastal belt of the Marmara Region Region. Particularly along the coastal belt, the temperature difference between summer and winter is not significant. Summers are relatively cool, while winters are mild on the coastal areas and snowy and cold in the higher altitudes. Due to precipitation occurring in every season in the Black Sea climate, there is no water shortage. The average temperature in January, the coldest month, is 4.2°C, while in July, the warmest month, it is 22.1°C, with an annual

average temperature of 13.0°C (Figure 1.11). The average annual total precipitation is 697.6 mm (Figure 1.12). These precipitation values exceed 2000 mm in the eastern Black Sea coastal areas around Rize. The share of summer precipitation in the annual total is 19.4%. The annual average relative humidity is 71% (DMİ, 2004).

Figure 1.11. Average Temperatures in the Black Sea Region (MGM2,2023)

Figure 1.12. Precipitation distribution by years in the Black Sea Region (MGM1, 2023).

2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

Bahadır (1991) examined the frequency and intensity of oppressive temperatures in Istanbul. The study investigated the daily course of oppressive heat, finding that maximum scores occurred around noon and minimum scores in the morning hours. It was also observed that severe oppressive heat occurred only during daytime hours. It was concluded that in Istanbul, oppressive heat typically occurs for short durations, with prolonged oppressive heat occurring in some years during July and August.

Kadıoğlu et al. (1992) developed a table of temperature and humidity indices. The study explored the effects of temperature and humidity on human health, demonstrating that the perceived temperatures differed from those measured meteorologically due to relative humidity. A table was prepared using the procedure used in the United States to determine these differences based on temperature and humidity values in Türkiye. In the conclusion, the effects of perceived temperature on human health based on temperature and humidity values were discussed.

Delworth et al. (1999) examined the effects of carbon dioxide-induced global warming on perceived temperatures (heat index). In their model spanning the period from 1765 to 2065, they found that hot and humid regions could be more affected. It was determined that among the regions most affected, the humid tropics and southeastern United States, India, southeastern Asia, and northern Australia were prominent.

Baloğlu (2001) studied the spatial variability of perceived temperatures in Türkiye. According to the study, the months of July and August are the most uncomfortable due to high temperatures and humidity. In this sense, discomfort is observed throughout Türkiye except for the northern regions of Eastern Anatolia, including Kars and Ardahan, and the high elevations of the Eastern Black Sea region. Moderate discomfort conditions prevail in most of the summer months along the Mediterranean and Southern Aegean Regionan coasts.

Deniz et al. (2003) examined the spatial distribution of perceived temperatures in the Marmara Region Region. The months of June, July, and August were found to reach dangerously high levels of perceived temperatures in the Marmara Region Region. The study found that in these months, even healthy individuals experienced disorders such as extreme fatigue, lack of concentration, and unwillingness, especially among the elderly and children.

Kim et al. (2006) conducted a time series analysis to predict the acute effects of high temperatures in six cities in South Korea and compared the temperature thresholds in daily mortality rates between cities. They examined the relationship between total mortality rates and daily average temperatures and heat indices in South Korea from 1994 to 2003. They determined the threshold temperatures to be between 27.0°C and 29.7°C for four cities. They calculated that a 1°C increase above the threshold values in Seoul, Daegu, Incheon, and Gwangju resulted in an estimated 16.3% increase in daily mortality rates. The study highlights the importance of regional differences in analyzing the effects of extreme heat events in assessing the impacts of climate change.

Zahid et al. (2010) found a significant increase in heat index trends during the summer season from 1961 to 2007 in various regions of Pakistan due to climate change. They identified a rising trend in almost all regions. The study found that the change in the Heat Index was associated with two factors: daytime temperature and relative humidity. According to the study, climate change not only leads to an increase in temperature but also alters precipitation patterns. The study also indicated that the increase in humidity during the summer season in almost all regions of the country is mainly due to monsoon rains.

Unal et al. (2013) examined the changes and trends in heatwaves in Western Anatolia from 1965 to 2006. The study found that heatwaves became more frequent after 1987. A significant and positive correlation was found between the increase in Mediterranean and Black Sea surface temperatures and heatwaves.

In addition to the mentioned studies, numerous researches have addressed the relationship between perceived temperature (heat index or humidex) and thermal comfort. These studies have increased as the effects of global warming have become more pronounced. Oleson et al. (2013) examined the variability of the humidex in summer for the United States and Southern Canada, comparing humidex values in urban and rural areas with dense populations.

Rana et al. (2013) investigated the use of the Humidex, which covers both temperature and humidity, as an easily measurable and representative indoor thermal comfort predictor. They confirmed the feasibility of Humidex as an indoor thermal comfort predictor by comparing its performance with the performance of the best feature set (the feature set that best predicts thermal comfort) created jointly using repeated

sequential forward selection and support vector regression. The analysis using global datasets, including data from seven climate regions on three continents, showed that Humidex is a preferred and easily measurable indoor thermal comfort descriptor in cases where humidity is significant.

Ropo et al. (2017) examined the variability and changes in the humidex for South Africa. They revealed that increasing temperatures due to climate change negatively impact the health of residents by causing an increase in the humidex.

Suparta et al. (2017) found a significant increase in the frequency of heatwaves over time in East Malaysia and attributed it to the rising temperatures due to global climate change.

Pan et al. (2019) investigated the effects of exposure to Humidex on the risk of hospitalization for childhood asthma in Hefei, China. The study associated low humidity with an increased risk of hospitalization for childhood asthma in Hefei. They found that children with asthma, especially girls and school-aged children, should avoid exposure to low-humidity environments. They concluded that Humidex plays a more important role than average temperature in public health in preventing diseases.

While some studies have examined the spatial and temporal changes in temperatures across Türkiye and certain geographical regions, only the spatial distribution of perceived temperatures (humidex) has been investigated. This study will be one of the first to reveal the variability and changes of humidex over time on the coasts of Türkiye.

3. MATERIAL and METHODS

3.1. Material

In the study, data obtained from the measurements conducted by the Turkish State Meteorological Service (TSMS) at meteorological stations operated by the General Directorate of Meteorology (GDM) in coastal regions of Türkiye over several years has been utilized. A minimum of 10 station data from each geographical region was selected, with emphasis on stations having minimal data loss. In other words, particular attention was given to selecting stations with the least data loss. The study primarily focuses on the period between 1990 and 2022, utilizing hourly measurements taken during the months of June, July, and August within this period.

The reason for selecting summer months is due to the fact that people are most affected by changes in humidex during these months (Garcia, 2019). Temperature and relative humidity (%) data measured between 05:00 and 16:00 UTC hours were employed in the study. Daily, monthly, and seasonal averages were calculated from these observational data, and maps and graphs were generated and interpreted accordingly. Data from 61 stations along the Turkish coast were utilized to evaluate the humidex characteristics of settlement areas (Table 3.1).

Throughout the study, temperature and relative humidity data were utilized, and absolute humidity calculations were also performed based on these data. Trend analyses were conducted by calculating absolute humidity values for years and months.

Hourly absolute humidity values were derived from the hourly temperature and relative humidity data using codes written in Python, a high-level programming language suitable for both procedural and object-oriented styles. After necessary data manipulations, these values were transformed into daily, monthly, and seasonal values and transferred to the netCDF data format. All methods employed in the thesis were converted into codes, and the data in netCDF format were analyzed using these codes. Matplotlib library was utilized for generating graphs, while ArcMap 10.8 package software was used for mapping purposes. MS Office was utilized for creating tables.

Geographic Information System (GIS) software, ArcMap 10.8, and SRTM DEM (Digital Elevation Model) data obtained from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website were used for spatial data selection and evaluation of terrain topographic

characteristics. The geographical coordinates of meteorological stations, i.e., location information, were overlaid onto the DEM data as point data.

Table 3.1. Regional distribution and coordinates of the meteorological stations taken as reference in the study

Station Name	Lat	Long	Station Name	Lat	Lat
1 Rize	41,04	40,5013	29 Edremit	39,5895	27,0192
2 Hopa	41,4065	41,433	30 Ayvalık	39,3113	26,6861
3 Akçaabat	41,0325	39,5615	31 Dikili	39,0737	26,888
4 Rize_Pazar	41,1777	40,8993	32 Konak	38,3949	27,0819
5 Ordu	40,9838	37,8858	33 Çeşme	38,3036	26,3724
6 Giresun	40,9227	38,3878	34 Kuşadası	37,8597	27,2652
7 Bafra	41,5515	35,9247	35 Efeler	37,8402	27,8379
8 Ünye	41,143	37,293	36 Bodrum	37,0328	27,4398
9 İnebolu	41,9789	33,7636	39 Datça	36,7083	27,6919
10 Sinop	42,0299	35,1545	40 Marmaris	36,8395	28,2452
11 Atakum	41,344167	36,2564	50 Selçuk	37,9423	27,3669
12 Bartın	41,6248	32,3569	51 Milas	37,3027	27,7804
13 Zonguldak	41,449242	31,7779	37 Dalaman	36,7719	28,7986
14 Amasra	41,7526	32,3827	38 Fethiye	36,6266	29,1238
15 Akçakoca	41,0895	31,1374	41 Alanya	36,5507	31,9803
16 Bandırma	40,3315	27,9965	42 Anamur	36,0686	32,8649
17 Çınarcık	40,6427	29,1063	43 Silifke	36,3824	33,9373
18 Gönen	40,1135	27,6426	44 Yenişehir	36,7808	34,6031
19 Çorlu	41,1798	27,816	45 Yüreğir	37,0041	35,3443
20 Kocaeli	40,7663	29,9173	46 İskenderun	36,5924	36,1582
21 Yalova	40,6589	29,2796	47 Finike	36,3024	30,1458
22 Tekirdağ	40,9585	27,4965	48 Burhaniye	39,4983	26,9755
23 Florya	40,9758	28,7865	49 Seferhisar	38,199	26,835
24 Sarıyer	41,1464	29,0502	52 Köyceğiz	36,97	28,6869
25 Şile	41,1688	29,6007	53 Manavgat	36,7895	31,441
26 Gökçeada	40,191	25,9075	54 Erdemli	36,6268	34,338
27 Bozcaada	39,8326	26,0728	55 Ceyhan	37,0153	35,7955
28 Çanakkale	40,141	26,3993	56 Dörtyol	36,8244	36,1981
			57 Demre	36,2421	29,979
			58 Gazipaşa	36,2715	32,3045
			59 Yumurtalık	36,7687	35,7903
			60 Karataş	36,5683	35,3894
			61 Samandağ	36,0814	35,9492

	Black Sea Region
	Marmara Region Region
	AAegean Regionan Region
	Mediterranean Region

3.2. Method

Çalışma kapsamında MGM'ye ait 61 istasyondan elde edilen saatlik hava sıcaklığı ve saatlik bağıl nem verileri, kayıp ve dış değerlerden arındırıldıktan sonra çok boyutlu netCDF formatına dönüştürülmüştür. Humidex hesaplaması için gerekli olan çiy noktası sıcaklığı, saatlik hava sıcaklığı ve saatlik bağıl nem değerleri kullanılarak elde edilmiştir. Saatlik humidex değerleri, saatlik hava sıcaklığı ve saatlik çiy noktası sıcaklıkları kullanılarak hesaplanmıştır (Figure 3.1). Saatlik mutlak nem değerleri, saatlik hava sıcaklığı ve saatlik bağıl nem değerleri kullanılarak hesaplanmıştır. Bu işlemler sonucunda saatlik hava sıcaklığı, saatlik bağıl nem, saatlik humidex ve saatlik mutlak nem olmak üzere her istasyona ait 33 yıllık dört değişken elde edilmiştir.

Figure 3.1. Variable transformations

The seasonal variables were subjected to the Mann-Kendall test, and regression tests were applied to the variables found significant at a 95% confidence level, followed by drawing regression lines and calculating trends. Subsequently, correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between the selected variables (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Work-flow chart

To interpret the trajectory or distribution of trend data obtained throughout the study along the Turkish coast, a coastal zone is envisioned as a 40 km wide band, or in other words, as a corridor. The data from stations where trend values are determined are subjected to IDW (Inverse Distance Weighting) interpolation to calculate the values for unknown locations. This method constructs a raster surface by estimating the unknown cell values inversely proportional to their distances, taking the average of all sample values within the specified search radius (Achilleos, 2011). Although it is acknowledged that meteorological data vary over short distances and periods, the primary objective sought through this method is to determine whether the distribution of trends is of a regional nature.

3.2.1. Dew Point Temperature Calculation

The dew point temperature represents the temperature at which the water vapor in an air parcel reaches its saturation level and begins to condense. In other words, it is the temperature at which the air parcel needs to be cooled in order to reach 100% humidity. The dew point varies depending on the moisture content and temperature of the air (Camuffo, 2014).

It is a key variable used in humidex calculations (Equation 3.2). Several equations have been developed to calculate the dew point temperature using air temperature and relative humidity (Vanderbei, 2012). However, these formulas do not universally calculate the dew point precisely. In this study, the Magnus-Tetens formula (Lawrence, 2005) was utilized as the dew point temperature calculator, providing accurate results (with a 0.35°C uncertainty) for temperatures ranging from -45°C to 60°C. The dew point temperature is calculated according to the following formula:

$$T_d = \frac{b \times \alpha(T, RH)}{a - \alpha(T, RH)} \quad (3.1)$$

Here;

T_d (°C) – Dew point temperature,

T (°C) – Air temperature,

RH – Relative humidity of the air,

$$\alpha(T, RH) = \ln\left(\frac{RH}{100}\right) + \left(\frac{a * T}{b + T}\right),$$

a and b are Magnus coefficients. As suggested by Alduchov et al., (1996), their values are:

$a = 17.625$ and

$b = 243.04$ °C

3.2.2. Humidex Calculation

In warm and humid weather, the temperature feels higher than it actually is. This is because the moisture-saturated or nearly saturated air prevents the sweat accumulated on our bodies from evaporating into the air. Consequently, individuals unable to lose heat through sweating perceive the temperature as higher than what is measured (Berglund, 1998).

The temperature we perceive, which differs from what the thermometer measures, is referred to as the humidex. In the exchange of heat between the body and the environment, if the heat loss from the body to the environment is excessive, the environment is perceived as cold or cool, whereas if the heat loss is insufficient, the environment is perceived as warm or oppressively hot. When there is thermal equilibrium between the body and the environment, individuals feel comfortable in their surroundings (Bahadır, 1991).

Thermal comfort is the state where individuals do not feel the need to alter the environmental conditions. In a state of thermal comfort, the interaction between an individual's body and the environmental conditions is minimal. Variables that play a significant role in an individual's thermal comfort or in heat loss or gain in the body, thereby forming the concept of "Humidex," include the following (Baloğlu, 2001):

- Air temperature (measured in the shade within a shelter)
- Ambient humidity (dependent on air temperature and humidity ratio)
- Level of activity (the energy generated in the body is a function of activity)
- Thermal resistance of clothing (varies according to the type and thickness of clothing)
- Mean radiant temperature (affected by the energy received directly from the sun and radiated by objects in the surroundings; can be measured with globe thermometers)
- Relative air velocity (dependent on wind speed and human activity)

Humidex depends on many variables as listed above, some of which may vary from person to person. To address this complexity, factors other than air temperature and relative humidity have been assumed constant. The reason for selecting these two variables is their significant impact on humidex and their measurability. Air temperature

Humidex Aralığı	Konfor Derecesi
20-29	Çok az konforsuz
30-39	Az konforsuz
40-45	Konforsuz
>45	Tehlikeli
>54	Sıcak çarpması

Figure 3.4. Effects of Humidex values on humans (Lukic, 2019)

3.2.3. Absolute Humidity Calculation

Absolute humidity is the actual amount of water vapor present in a specific volume of air. Absolute humidity (AH) is defined as the mass of water vapor (m) per unit volume (V) of air (Green et al., 2009). Although calculations typically express the amount of water vapor in a cubic meter of air in kilograms in accordance with the SI unit system, recent presentations convert it to grams (Huang et al., 2023).

$$AH = \frac{m}{V} \text{ (kg/m}^3\text{)} = \text{(kg} \cdot 10^3\text{/m}^3\text{)} \quad (3.3)$$

If the relative humidity and air temperature are known, the absolute humidity can be calculated using the following equation (3.4):

$$AH = \frac{RH \cdot e_s}{R_w \cdot T \cdot 100} \quad (3.4)$$

Here;

- AH – Mutlak nem ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$),
- RH – Relative humidity (%),
- e_s – Saturated water vapor pressure ($hPa = \frac{N}{m^2}$),
- $R_w = 461.5 \left(\frac{J}{kg \cdot K} = \frac{N \cdot m}{kg \cdot K} \right)$ – Specific gas constant for water vapor,
- T (°K) – Air temperature.

According to the equation proposed by Bolton (1980), the saturated vapor pressure (eS) of water at a given temperature T can be written in the following Figure (3.5):

$$e_s(t) = 6.112 * e^y \quad (3.5)$$

Here;

- $e_s(t)$ – Doymuş su buharı basıncı (hPA),
- $t(^{\circ}\text{C})$ – Air temperature,
- $y = \left(\frac{17.67*t}{t + 243.5}\right)$ – Empirical variable.

3.2.4. Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a method of analysis that allows prediction of events to occur after known findings in previous steps. In this analytical method, a scatter plot of variables' known values is constructed or assumed to exist. A line passing closest to the paired data points on this plot is drawn, termed as the regression or trend line. The regression line has a slope and an equation. This equation is expressed as follows (3.6) (Fahrmeir et al., 2009):

$$y = \hat{b}_0 + \hat{b}_1 \quad (3.6)$$

\hat{b}_0 = It is a regression constant. It is the point where the regression line intersects the y-axis.

\hat{b}_1 = Regression coefficient (slope). It indicates the change in the y variable's own unit for a one-unit increase in the x variable. The slope of the regression line is calculated in several different ways. In this study, Sen's trend slope method, which is widely used and highly reliable in climate research, will be employed.

3.2.5. Sen's Trend Slope Method

The determination of the linear slopes (rate of change over unit time) of trends is conducted for the purpose of this study. This non-parametric method, developed by Sen (1968) and proposed by Hirsch et al. (1982), is not affected by data errors and outliers (Burn et al., 2002).

It can be applied to records containing missing values. According to this method, the trend slope x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n of time-ordered data is calculated using the following

equation, where x_j and x_k are the data at any j and k times, respectively (with the condition $j > k$) (Partal, 2002).

$$\beta = \frac{(x_j - x_k)}{(j - k)} \quad (3.7)$$

The number of all β values found is denoted as N . The data, comprising $N = n(n+1)/2$ observations, is arranged in ascending order. The median value of these arranged data provides us with the rate of change per unit time. This method merely determines the slope of the existing trend. However, it does not ascertain the significance of the slope or its level of significance. To measure the reliability of the slope obtained through the trend slope method, the Mann-Kendall test is applied to the data.

3.2.6. Mann-Kendall Test

The Mann-Kendall test, a specialized application of the test known as Kendall's Tau (Yu et al., 1993), is a non-parametric test. This method, most commonly applied in the analysis of hydroclimatological data and cited as a method for detecting trends, is based on the ranks of values rather than their magnitudes (Partal, 2002).

Mondal et al. (2012) applied the Mann-Kendall (MK) Test to 40 years of daily rainfall data from 1971 to 2010 to examine the changing trend of rainfall in a river basin near the coastal region of Orissa.

Chattopadhyay et al. (2012) applied the Mann-Kendall (MK) Test to study the spatial distribution of tropospheric ozone and observed a linear trend in spatial distribution in all seasons except the Monsoon (JJAS).

Rehman (2013) investigated long-term wind speed trends using the Mann-Kendall statistical trend analysis method. Historical daily average wind speed data measured at a height of 8-12 m above ground level at national and international airports in Saudi Arabia over a period of 37 years were used to obtain annual and monthly average wind speeds and annual average wind speed trends. A decreasing trend of 0.01852 m/s per year was observed in annual average wind speed values.

In this test, the time-ordered series (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are random variables assumed to be independent of time and identically distributed under the null hypothesis H_0 . Under the alternative hypothesis H_1 , where $(k > j)$ and n is the length of the data record,

the distribution of consecutive data values x_k and x_j in the series is not similar, indicating a linear trend in the series (Partal, 2002). The test statistic S for the Mann-Kendall test is calculated as follows (3.8):

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) \quad (3.8)$$

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = \begin{cases} \text{eğer}(x_j - x_k) > 0 \Rightarrow +1 \\ \text{eğer}(x_j - x_k) = 0 \Rightarrow 0 \\ \text{eğer}(x_j - x_k) < 0 \Rightarrow -1 \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

The variance of the test statistic S , which has an asymptotically normal distribution and has a mean of zero, is found in the following figure (3.10):

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18} \quad (3.10)$$

If there are similar values in the data (ties), the following equation (3.11) is used instead of (3.10) for the calculation of variance:

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_t t(t-1)(2t+5)}{18} \quad (3.11)$$

Whether the variance of the established Mann-Kendall test is significant is determined by comparing the calculated value of the standard normal variable z with the critical z value as calculated by the following equation (3.12):

In this expression, the numbers in the denominator represent continuity correction units.

$$z = \begin{cases} S > 0 \Rightarrow \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} \\ S = 0 \Rightarrow 0 \\ S < 0 \Rightarrow \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} \end{cases} \quad (3.12)$$

The z-value here is deemed to accept the null hypothesis H_0 if it is less than or equal to the $Z_{\alpha/2}$ value determined from standard normal distribution tables at a specific α significance level; otherwise, it is rejected. The Mann-Kendall test statistic, denoted by S, indicates the presence of a decreasing trend if negative and an increasing trend if positive. In this study, changes at the $\alpha=0.95$ confidence level are considered in map and graph plotting. Trends below the $\alpha=0.95$ significance level in maps are denoted by black bold points. Regression lines are not drawn for variables exhibiting trends below the $\alpha=0.95$ confidence level in graphs.

3.2.7. Correlation Analysis

Correlation is a measure of the relationship between two variables, which can be either positive or negative. In a positive relationship, as one variable increases, the other also increases, or as one decreases, the other decreases. In a negative relationship, however, as one variable increases, the other decreases. The strength of this positive or negative relationship is determined by the correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient is calculated using the following equation (3.13) (Good, 2009):

$$r = \frac{\sum xy - \frac{\sum x \sum y}{n}}{\sqrt{\left(\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n}\right)\left(\sum y^2 - \frac{(\sum y)^2}{n}\right)}} \quad (3.13)$$

Here;

- r , it is the Pearson Correlation Coefficient.
- n , represents the number of data points.
- x , refers to the values of the first variable.
- y , refers to the values of the second variable.

The correlation coefficient takes values ranging from -1 to +1 and is denoted by r (Gogtay et al., 2017);

$r > 0$ Positive correlation

$r < 0$ Negative correlation

$r = 0$ No linear relationship

As the correlation coefficient rr moves away from zero, the relationship increases, whereas it decreases as rr approaches zero. Although a non-zero value of rr implies a relationship between variables, the magnitude of this relationship is also crucial. Hence, it is necessary to establish a threshold value in the conducted analyses. This threshold value, indicating which correlation coefficient is considered significant, is determined through a t-test (Orhunbilge, 1996).

3.2.8. Relative Humidity

The relative humidity in an air parcel is the ratio of the actual water vapor content in the parcel to the maximum water vapor content the parcel can hold at the same temperature (Davis et al., 2016). It is typically expressed as a percentage.

$$Bağlı\ nem = \frac{mutlak\ nem\ (\frac{g}{m^3})}{parselin\ taşıyabileceği\ maksimum\ su\ buharı\ miktarı\ (\frac{g}{m^3})} 100 \quad (3.14)$$

3.2.9. Maximum Moisture Carrying Capacity

The maximum moisture carrying capacity is the maximum amount of moisture that an air parcel can carry at a specific temperature. Maximum moisture carrying capacity (MMCC) is defined as the mass of water vapor (m) per unit volume (V) of air in cubic units. Although calculations express water vapor in kilograms per cubic meter of air according to the SI unit system, recent representations have been converted and used in grams.

$$MMCC = \frac{m}{V} (kg/m^3) = (kg * 10^3/m^3) \quad (3.15)$$

If the air temperature is known, the maximum moisture carrying capacity can be calculated using the following equation (3.16):

$$MMCC = \frac{RH * es}{R_w * T * 100} \quad (3.16)$$

Burada;

- MMCC – Maximum moisture carrying capacity ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$),
- RH – Relative humidity (%), Since the air parcel is considered saturated, it will be taken as RH=100.
- e_s – Saturated water vapor pressure ($hPa = \frac{N}{m^2}$),
- $R_w = 461.5 \left(\frac{J}{kg \cdot K} = \frac{N \cdot m}{kg \cdot K} \right)$ – Specific gas constant for water vapor is,
- T (°K) – Air temperature.

According to the equation proposed by Bolton (1980), the saturated vapor pressure (e_s) of water at a given temperature t can be written as (3.17):

$$e_s(t) = 6.112 * e^y \quad (3.17)$$

Here;

- $e_s(t)$ – Saturated water vapor pressure (hPa),
- t(°C) – Air temperature,
- $y = \left(\frac{17.67 * t}{t + 243.5} \right)$ – empirical variable.

As the air temperature increases, the moisture-carrying capacity of the air increases (Figure 3.3). If the absolute amount of humidity is kept constant and the air temperature is increased, the relative humidity decreases.

Figure 3.5. The relationship between air temperature and maximum humidity transport. MMCC values were obtained with the help of equation (3.15).

3.2.10. Reasons for the Selection of Sample Stations

The data from stations located in 61 different settlements along the coastal regions of Türkiye were utilized in this study. However, due to the anticipated excessive expansion of the thesis volume if each station were to be included in the content, certain sample stations were selected and examined for inclusion in the text based on the reasons specified below, with their graphs presented within the text. Graphs for the remaining stations are provided in the appendices section (Appendix 1). Data pertaining to temperature, humidex, relative humidity, and absolute humidity trend values for all stations were summarized in tabular form.

The station in the Pazar district of Rize was selected as the only station among the 61 stations with a positive relative humidity trend. The Giresun station was chosen as the only station in the Black Sea Region with an increasing absolute humidity trend. The

Samsun Atakum station was selected due to being one of the most densely populated areas in the Black Sea Region.

The Sarıyer station was chosen as it exhibited the highest increase in absolute humidity among stations in Istanbul. The Çanakkale station was selected as the station in the Marmara Region Region with the greatest decrease in relative humidity.

The Çeşme station was selected as it had the lowest humidex increase trend among the stations studied along the Turkish coasts. The Kuşadası station was chosen for having the highest positive trend in absolute humidity in the Aegean Regionan Region.

The Alanya station was selected for having the highest absolute humidity trend in the Mediterranean Region. The Samandağ station was chosen due to the absence of a significant humidex trend.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS and DISCUSSION

4.1. Humidex Analysis on the Coasts of Türkiye

4.1.1. Analysis of the Coasts of Türkiye

Upon examining the temperature and humidex values of the coasts of Türkiye, it is observed that both temperature and humidex values have increased over the years (Figure 4.1). There is a very high positive correlation between these two variables, with $r=0.913$. This correlation coefficient indicates that temperature and humidex are directly proportional along the coasts of Türkiye. However, the rate of increase for each variable is not the same. A one-unit increase in air temperature has resulted in approximately a two-unit increase in humidex. Over a decade, while the temperature has increased by $0.635\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the humidex has increased by $1.293\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. From 1990 to 2022, the average temperature rose by $2.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the average humidex increased by $4.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The relatively lower increase in temperature has caused a higher increase in humidex. This suggests that thermal comfort may deteriorate more rapidly than the rate of temperature increase. In the 1990s, the humidex was around $32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. According to the literature, humidex values between $30\text{-}39\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are characterized as "Uncomfortable." Since 1990, the humidex has steadily increased, and the average humidex on the coasts of Türkiye has recently exceeded $36\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 4.1). This indicates that thermal comfort has deteriorated more significantly compared to 30 years ago.

In recent years, there has been a decreasing trend in the relative humidity on the coasts of Türkiye (Figure 4.2). The decrease in relative humidity is due to the increased air temperature, which enhances the air's capacity to hold moisture. As seen in Figure 4.2, it is understood that the decreasing trend in relative humidity does not mitigate or affect the increasing trend in humidex. In this study, absolute humidity trend values have been examined to better understand the humidex trend.

Figure 4.1. The trend of the summer humidex and air temperature averages of the 61 stations along the coasts of Türkiye (Figure 3.1) throughout the analysis period (1990-2022).

Figure 4.2. The trend of the summer humidex and relative humidity averages of the 61 stations along the coasts of Türkiye (Figure 3.1) throughout the analysis period (1990-2022).

When examining the absolute humidity trend, it is understood that there is no significant trend within the 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.3). Although the absolute humidity rate has not changed, the increase in temperature has led to approximately a twofold increase in the humidex. In this case, it can be stated that if there were a possible increasing trend in absolute humidity, the humidex would increase significantly more.

Figure 4.3. The trend of the summer air temperature and absolute humidity averages of the 61 stations along the coasts of Türkiye (Figure 3.1) throughout the analysis period (1990-2022).

Figure 4.4. The trend of the summer humidex and absolute humidity averages of the 61 stations along the coasts of Türkiye (Figure 3.1) throughout the analysis period (1990-2022).

4.1.2. Distribution of Humidex

When examining the summer air temperature data of the coasts of Türkiye, it is understood that there is an increasing temperature trend in all 61 stations (Figure 4.5). This is due to the rise in global air temperatures (Güler et al., 2023). Here, the minimum temperature increase is observed in Çeşme at 0.252 °C/decade and the maximum in İnebolu at 1.1168 °C/decade. The Black Sea and Marmara Region regions exhibit relatively higher air temperature trends.

When examining the summer humidex data of the coasts of Türkiye, an increasing humidex trend is observed at fifty-five stations, except for six (Figure 4.6). The humidex trend at each station is greater than the temperature trend. The humidex trends in the Black Sea and Marmara Region regions are relatively higher.

When examining the relative humidity data, it is generally observed to have a negative trend (Figure 4.7). However, the relative humidity increased at the Pazar station. In general, the negative trend in relative humidity values is due to the increased air temperature, which raises the air's moisture-carrying capacity and thereby reduces

relative humidity (Equation 3.14; Equation 3.16). Therefore, having negative trends in relative humidity does not imply that the amount of moisture in the air has decreased.

When examining the absolute humidity data and the trends of increase and decrease, it is understood that there are positive absolute humidity trends in most parts of the Black Sea, the northern Marmara Region region, and some stations in the AAegean Regionan and Mediterranean regions (Figure 4.8). In stations where positive absolute humidity trends are observed, the humidex has increased relatively more. In stations where there is no significant absolute humidity trend, the humidex has increased less compared to stations with positive absolute humidity trends. The stations where the humidex has increased the least are those with negative trends in absolute humidity. These places are also among the ones where thermal comfort deteriorates more slowly. Some of these stations include Yenişehir, Marmaris, Çeşme, Seferhisar, Çanakkale, and Giresun.

Figure 4.5. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer air temperatures along the coasts of Türkiye.

Figure 4.6. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer humidex values along the coasts of Türkiye.

Figure 4.7. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer relative humidity values along the coasts of Türkiye.

Figure 4.8. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer absolute humidity values along the coasts of Türkiye.

4.1.3. Analysis Findings of Sample Stations

This section focuses on the analysis findings based on the examined data from selected sample stations in various coastal regions of Turkey. Here, for each station, the variations and changes in parameters are visually and numerically examined through graphs of air temperature-humidex, humidex-relative humidity, air temperature-relative humidity, and humidex-absolute humidity (Table 3.1 and Table 4.1).

Table 4.1. The decadal trends of summer months along the coasts of Turkey from 1990 to 2022. NSC: No significant trend within the 95% confidence interval.

	Station Name	t (°C/dec)	hx (°C/dec)	rh (%/dec)	ah (g/m ³ .dec)	(90-22) Mean_t	(90-22) Mean_hx
0	Mean Türkiye Coasts	0,635	1,293	-1,379	NSC	27,71	33,57
1	Rize	0,753	0,844	NSC	0,512	24,86	32,58
2	Hopa	0,47	NSC	NSC	NSC	24,56	32,56
3	Akçaabat	0,931	0,841	-2,126	NSC	24,54	31,51
4	Rize_Pazar	0,697	1,204	3,822	1,108	23,54	30,55
5	Ordu	0,36	NSC	NSC	NSC	24,87	32,14
6	Giresun	0,729	NSC	-3,144	-0,393	24,02s	31,04
7	Bafra	0,655	1,675	NSC	0,622	24,78	30,13
8	Ünye	0,76	1,672	-1,207	0,707	24,25	30,62
9	İnebolu	1,168	2,492	-1,747	1,045	24,17	29,89
10	Sinop	0,833	2,286	NSC	1,359	24,16	30,69
11	Atakum	0,667	1,325	-2,032	0,38	24,82	30,79
12	Bartın	0,945	2,267	-5,833	0,394	25,0ca	29,73
13	Zonguldak	0,819	2,019	NSC	1,169	23,25	28,75
14	Amasra	0,817	1,561	NSC	0,64	23,22	28,93
15	Akçakoca	0,9	2,406	NSC	1,145	24,04	30,43
16	Bandırma	0,669	1,548	NSC	NSC	25,52	30,84
17	Çınarcık	0,809	1,325	-4,306	NSC	25,41	31,63
18	Gönen	0,564	1,748	-4,403	NSC	27,07	31,26
19	Çorlu	0,626	1,102	-5,952	NSC	25,87	30,2
20	Kocaeli	0,802	1,776	-4,34	NSC	26,24	31,26
21	Yalova	0,435	1,449	-2,115	0,483	25,88	31,75
22	Tekirdağ	0,656	1,443	-3,146	NSC	25,61	31,08
23	Florya	0,753	1,558	-2,583	0,459	26,01	31,86
24	Sarıyer	0,697	1,882	NSC	0,998	24,75	31,09
25	Şile	0,914	1,665	-4,273	0,33	24,74	31,56
26	Gökçeada	0,495	1,276	-2,324	NSC	26,66	31,05
27	Bozcaada	0,95	1,542	-4,052	NSC	24,27	29,68
28	Çanakkale	0,722	0,679	-8,961	-1,024	27,26	32,33

Table 4.1. (Continuation) Decadal trends in summer months along the Turkish coasts between 1990 and 2022. NSC: No significant trend within a 95% confidence interval.

	Station	t	hx	rh	ah	(90-22)	(90-22)
	Name	(°C/dec)	(°C/dec)	(%/dec)	(g/m³.dec)	Mean_t	Mean_hx
30	Ayvalık	0,514	NSC	-9,657	-1,765	28.82	34.17
31	Dikili	0,413	0,771	-5,089	-0,466	27.27	32.93
32	Konak	0,286	0,61	-3,917	NSC	29.81	34.04
33	Çeşme	0,252	0,29	-4,71	-0,548	27.71	34.23
34	Kuşadası	0,445	1,848	NSC	1,036	28.07	32.89
35	Efeler	0,422	1,247	-4,591	NSC	31.31	34.73
36	Bodrum	0,775	1,544	-3,466	NSC	30.58	34.83
37	Datça	0,74	1,251	NSC	0,448	29.25	34.81
38	Marmaris	0,374	0,559	-4,784	-0,585	30.91	35.99
39	Burhaniye	0,625	1,753	NSC	NSC	29.16	32.1
40	Seferhisar	0,47	0,905	-5,753	-0,541	29.52	33.56
41	Selçuk	0,42	2,073	-2,734	0,579	30.02	32.64
42	Milas	0,591	1,388	-6,43	-0,538	32.07	35.21
43	Dalaman	0,517	NSC	-6,09	-0,702	30.69	36.47
44	Fethiye	0,685	1,787	-4,223	NSC	30.87	35.68
45	Alanya	0,854	1,964	-1,39	0,841	29.08	38.66
46	Anamur	0,555	1,144	-4,807	NSC	29.41	37.97
47	Silifke	0,792	1,161	-6,352	NSC	30.39	37.29
48	Yenişehir	0,847	0,921	-5,537	-0,38	29.25	38.5
49	Yüreğir	0,383	0,846	-4,318	NSC	30.39	38.17
50	İskenderun	0,617	0,933	-3,086	NSC	28.85	37.81
51	Finike	0,396	1,13	-4,84	NSC	30.58	36.26
52	Köyceğiz	0,426	1,775	-2,487	0,336	32.06	36.15
53	Manavgat	0,84	1,906	-2,633	NSC	30.62	36.44
54	Erdemli	0,333	1,069	-1,682	NSC	29.17	37.27
55	Ceyhan	0,539	1,758	-3,989	NSC	30.09	35.74
56	Dört Yol	0,539	1,612	NSC	NSC	29.03	35.67
57	Demre	0,959	1,416	-4,904	NSC	30.82	36.78
58	Gazipaşa	0,472	1,408	-2,845	NSC	29.19	34.96
59	Yumurtalık	0,638	1,077	-4,787	NSC	28.86	37.44
60	Karataş	0,548	1,401	NSC	0,589	28.04	36.9
61	Samandağ	0,531	NSC	-5,753	-0,798	27.96	38.07

When the daytime humidex and air temperature graphs of Pazar district in Rize were examined over many years, it was observed that while the air temperature increased by $0.697\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ per decade, the humidex increased by $1.204\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 4.9.a). The Pazar station is the only station among those studied that shows a positive relative humidity trend (Figure 4.7). The relative humidity trend is calculated as 3.822% per decade, which is quite high (Figure 4.9.b). There has been an increase of 1.108 g/m^3 in absolute humidity (Figure 4.9.c).

Figure 4.9. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Pazar. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity.

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Giresun, an increase of $0.729^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ in air temperature was observed, while no significant trend in humidex was found within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.10.a). Upon analyzing the air temperature and humidex graph, despite the increase in air temperature, a negative trend in absolute humidity is evident (Figure 4.10c). The positive effect of air temperature on humidex has been attenuated by the decrease in absolute humidity. Therefore, a significant increase in humidex has not been observed.

Figure 4.10. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Giresun. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When analyzing the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex averages in Atakum, it is observed that air temperature increased by 0.667°C per decade, while humidex increased by 1.325°C per decade (Figure 4.11.a). The trend in relative humidity values was found to be -2.032% /decade (Figure 4.11.b). There is an increasing trend of 0.38 g/m^3 per decade in absolute humidity values, thus humidex has been influenced by both air temperature and absolute humidity (Figure 4.11.d).

Figure 4.11. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Atakum. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Sariyer, it is observed that air temperature increased by 0.697°C per decade, while humidex showed a higher increase of 1.882°C per decade (Figure 4.12.a). No significant trend in relative humidity was found within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.12.b). There is a trend of 0.998 g/m^3 in absolute humidity (Figure 4.12.c).

Figure 4.12. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Sariyer. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Çanakkale, during the decade analyzed, an increase of 0.722°C in air temperature was observed, while humidex showed a slight increase of 0.679°C (Figure 4.13.a). There is a trend of $-8.961\%/decade$ in relative humidity (Figure 4.13.b), and a trend of -1.024 g/m^3 per decade in absolute humidity (Figure 4.13.c). The reason why the trend in humidex is less than the trend in air temperature is due to the attenuation of the positive effect of air temperature on humidex by the negative trend in absolute humidity.

Figure 4.13. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Çanakkale. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Çeşme, during the analyzed decade, there was an increase of $0.252^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ in air temperature, while humidex showed an increase of $0.29^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ (Figure 4.14.a). The graph of relative humidity reveals a trend of $-4.71\%/\text{decade}$ (Figure 4.14.b), and the absolute humidity graph shows a trend of $-0.548\text{ g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 4.14.c). Increased air temperatures generally lead to increased evaporation, hence absolute humidity tends to rise.

Figure 4.14. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Çeşme. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Kuşadası, a temperature increase of $0.445^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ was observed, while humidex showed a higher increase of 1.848°C (Figure 4.15.a). There was no significant trend observed in relative humidity (Figure 4.15b). In absolute humidity, there was a trend of $1.036 \text{ g}/\text{m}^3$ during the decade analyzed (Figure 4.15c).

Figure 4.15. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Kuşadası. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Alanya, during the analyzed decade, there was an increase of 0.854°C in air temperature, while humidex showed an increase of 1.964°C (Figure 4.16.a). The graph of relative humidity shows a trend of $-1.39\%/\text{decade}$ (Figure 4.16.b), and there was an increase of 0.841 g/m^3 per decade in absolute humidity (Figure 4.16.c).

Figure 4.16. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Alanya. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term daytime air temperature and humidex values in Samandağ, a temperature increase of $0.531^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ was observed, while no significant trend in humidex was found within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.17.a). There is a high trend of $-5.753\%/\text{decade}$ in relative humidity values (Figure 4.17.b). The absolute humidity graph shows a trend of $-0.798\text{ g}/\text{m}^3$ during the analyzed decade. The increase in air temperature has been attenuated by the decrease in absolute humidity, hence no significant trend is observed in humidex.

Figure 4.17. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in Samandağ. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

4.1.4. Regional Analysis

When examining the long-term summer data along the Marmara Region coasts, it is observed that the air temperature trend is $0.692^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$, while the humidex trend is $1.55^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ (Figure 4.19.a). The coastal areas of the Marmara Region exhibit the highest humidex trend of $1.55^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ among the studied coastal regions. In terms of relative humidity values along the Marmara Region coasts, there is a significant negative trend of $-1.286\%/\text{dec}$ within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.19.b). Absolute humidity increased by $0.329\text{ g}/\text{m}^3$ per decade, showing a correlation of $r=0.51$ with air temperature. From these data, it can be inferred that the increasing air temperature enhances evaporation along the Marmara Region coasts. Furthermore, there is a correlation of $r=0.729$ between absolute humidity and humidex (Figure 4.19.c).

Figure 4.18. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in the Black Sea Region. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term summer data along the Marmara Region coasts, it is observed that the air temperature trend is $0.692^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$, while the humidex trend is $1.55^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ (Figure 4.19.a). The coastal areas of the Marmara Region exhibit the highest humidex trend of $1.55^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ among the studied coastal regions. In terms of relative humidity values along the Marmara Region coasts, there is a significant negative trend of $-1.286\%/\text{dec}$ within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.19.b). Absolute humidity increased by $0.329\text{ g}/\text{m}^3$ per decade, showing a correlation of $r=0.51$ with air temperature. From these data, it can be inferred that the increasing air temperature enhances evaporation along the Marmara Region coasts. Furthermore, there is a correlation of $r=0.729$ between absolute humidity and humidex, indicating a strong relationship (Figure 4.19.c).

Figure 4.19. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in the Marmara Region. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term summer data along the Aegean Region coasts, it is understood that the air temperature trend is $0.478^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$, while the humidex trend is $1.087^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{dec}$ (Figure 4.20.a). There is a significant negative trend of $-1.743\text{ }/\text{decade}$ in relative humidity values (Figure 4.20.b). However, there was no significant increase observed in absolute humidity within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.20.c). The absence of a significant absolute humidity trend has contributed to the smaller increase in humidex compared to other regions. Nevertheless, even with stable absolute humidity values, a one-unit increase in air temperature can lead to more than a one-unit increase in humidex, as observed along the Aegean Region coasts.

Figure 4.20. Aegean Region'nin yaz ayları ortalamalarının uzun yıllar (1990-2012) seyri. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When examining the long-term summer data along the Mediterranean Region coasts, it is observed that the air temperature trend is $0.604\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/decade}$, while the humidex trend is $1.265\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/dec}$ (Figure 4.21.a). There is a significant negative trend of (-1.743 \%/dec) in relative humidity values (Figure 4.21.b). However, no significant trend was found in absolute humidity within a 95% confidence interval (Figure 4.21.c).

Figure 4.21. The long-term trends (1990-2022) of summer means in the Mediterranean Region. a) Long-term trends of air temperature and humidex. b) Long-term trends of relative humidity and humidex. c) Long-term trends of air temperature and absolute humidity. d) Long-term trends of humidex and absolute humidity

When coastal regions are considered together, it is observed that humidex shows an increasing trend across all coasts, exceeding 1°C per decade. The highest humidex trend value, at 1.376°C per decade, is found along the Black Sea Region coasts (Table 4.2). Additionally, the highest air temperature trend (0.767°C/decade) and absolute humidity trend (0.619 g/m³.dec) are also observed in the Black Sea Region. The lowest humidex trend (1.087°C/decade) is observed along the Aegean Region coasts. Despite no significant trend in absolute humidity values along the Aegean Region coasts, relative humidity values (-1.743%/decade) have decreased more compared to other coastal regions.

Table 4.2. Long-term trends of the regions. NSC: No significant trend within a 95% confidence interval.

Region name	Air temperature trend (°C/dec)	Humidex trend (°C/dec)	Relative humidity trend (%/dec)	Absolut humidity trend (g/m³.dec)
Türkiye's coasts	0.635	1.293	-1.379	NSC
Black Sea Reg.	0.767	1.376	NSC	0.619
Marmara Region	0.692	1.55	-1.286	0.329
Aegean Region	0.478	1.087	-1.743	NSC
Mediterranean R.	0.604	1.265	-2.167	NSC

4.1.5. Interpolation Maps of Turkiye's Coasts

Considering the meteorological data's variability over short distances, which affects parameters like humidex, IDW interpolation method was employed to interpret findings regionally along the coastal strip. To achieve this, a 40 km-wide zone extending from the coastline to inland areas was defined. Station findings where trends were identified were extrapolated to locations without data based on distance, thus forming coastal trend values (Figure 4.22). The selection of a 40 km-wide line was purely to visualize the trend's coastal changes on the map scale. Using the interpolation maps obtained from the study, the distributions of temperature, absolute humidity, relative humidity, and humidex trend values along the coastline were analyzed (Figure 4.22.a.b.c.d).

Examination of trend data in the interpolation maps reveals an increase in air temperature and humidex along all coastlines. The highest temperature increase trends are observed along the Western Black Sea Region coastlines, particularly between Sinop and Akçakoca, whereas the lowest temperature increase trends are seen along the Aegean Region coastlines between Dikili and Seferihisar (Figure 4.22.a).

Regarding absolute humidity values, the highest increasing trend is noted along the Black Sea Region coastlines near Akçakoca, Zonguldak, İnebolu, Sinop, and Rize-Pazar, while a negative trend is more prevalent along the Aegean Region coastlines (Figure 4.22.b). The lack of significant trends in nearly half of the stations regarding absolute humidity resulted in a predominance of yellow tones in the interpolation.

In terms of relative humidity values, more than 40 stations exhibit a negative trend, prominently seen in the Aegean and Mediterranean Region coastlines (Figure 4.22.c). This is attributed to increased air humidity due to rising temperature trends.

Locations with high humidex trends correspond to those with high absolute humidity trends, such as İnebolu, Sinop, Sarıyer, Çanakkale, Selçuk, Datça, Alanya, and Karataş (Figure 4.22.b; Figure 4.22.d). Areas with the lowest humidex trends include the Burhaniye-Seferihisar stretch, Ordu-Akçaabat area, and around Hopa; however, all these regions still show an increasing humidex trend. The coastal segments where the highest trends are concentrated include the Sinop-Sarıyer stretch in the Western Black Sea Region and the Manavgat-Alanya area in the Mediterranean Region (Figure 4.22.d)."

Figure 4.22. Interpolations of long-term (1990-2022) summer means of Türkiye's coasts. a) Air temperature interpolation. b) Absolute humidity interpolation. c) Relative humidity interpolation. d) Humidex interpolation.

4.2. Discussion

There are several studies focusing on perceived temperatures in Turkey at the provincial and regional levels. Notable among these studies are:

- Bahadır (1991): Examined the frequency and intensity of oppressive temperatures in Istanbul.
- Kadioğlu et al. (1992): Investigated the impact of temperature and humidity on human health by preparing a temperature and humidity index table.
- Baloğlu (2001): Examined the spatial variability of perceived temperatures in Turkey.
- Deniz et al. (2003): Analyzed the spatial distribution of perceived temperatures in the Marmara Region.

These studies underscore the significant impact of perceived temperatures on human health in Turkey. However, they are perceived to have certain shortcomings:

- Most studies are limited to specific regions or provinces.
- Comprehensive studies using current data are lacking.
- Relative humidity is typically used in vapor (humidity) analyses, which can lead to inaccuracies.

This study represents the most comprehensive and up-to-date analysis of perceived temperatures across all Turkish coasts using the humidex method. The importance of this study is summarized as follows:

- It covers all coastal stations in Turkey with suitable data.
- Current data were utilized.
- Absolute humidity was used in humidity analyses.
- High data quality enhances the reliability of findings.

In previous studies analyzing perceived temperatures, relative humidity has often been used to analyze vapor content. However, using relative humidity for perceived temperature analyses can lead to misconceptions and erroneous findings. This study employs absolute humidity for vapor analysis to mitigate such issues. Additionally,

relative humidity analysis was also conducted, emphasizing potential errors associated with its use in such studies.

Various parameters are used in the analysis of perceived temperatures. This study employs the humidex index, which, though unitless, is presented in Celsius degrees for clarity and ease of understanding in this research.

Stations with zero missing data among all coastal stations were selected for data collection (Figure 1.1). Data were utilized after being cleansed of outliers, with significance tests applied to ensure only statistically significant trends within a 0.95 confidence interval were included in the analysis. High data quality enhances the reliability of findings.

Hourly data from 1990 to 2023 during daytime hours (05:00-16:00 UTC) were used for humidex calculations. Daytime hours were chosen due to the tendency for severe oppressive temperatures to occur during these periods (Bahadır, 1991). All calculations were based on averages of hourly data.

Key findings from the analysis include:

- Observations indicate an increase in air temperature across all examined coasts (Figure 4.5).
- Increases in air temperature have also elevated the humidex.
- Humidex trends exhibit spatial variability (Figure 4.6).
- There is a positive relationship between absolute humidity trends and humidex trends. Locations with positive absolute humidity trends show higher humidex increases (Figure 4.6; Figure 4.8).
- No significant relationship was established between relative humidity and humidex trends (Figure 4.6; Figure 4.7).
- A 1-unit increase in air temperature results in approximately a 2-unit increase in humidex (Figure 4.1).
- With global warming effects, further increases in humidex values are anticipated in the future (IPCC, 2023).

The findings of this study could have significant implications for various sectors such as human health, agriculture, and tourism. These impacts include:

- Elevated humidex values may lead to heat stress and related health issues.
- Vulnerable populations such as the elderly, children, and individuals with chronic illnesses are particularly at risk.
- Heat stress can cause fatigue, headaches, muscle cramps, dizziness, fainting, and potentially death.
- Hospitals may experience increased admissions and occupancy rates.
- Work productivity may decline.
- Increased humidex values could adversely affect tourist comfort.
- Participation in outdoor activities may decrease during hot weather.
- Certain tourist destinations may become less attractive.
- Tourism revenues may decrease.
- Elevated humidex values can influence energy consumption.
- Increased use of air conditioning during hot weather may strain electricity supply.

This study analyzed the regional distribution of humidex along the coasts, emphasizing the need for detailed analyses in densely populated areas experiencing high trends. Analyzing future trends in humidex using IPCC scenarios or ensemble models could provide clearer insights into the future of coastal thermal comfort.

The study did not evaluate specific locations of selected stations. Furthermore, the impact of wind on perceived temperature values was not addressed, which is related to the absence of wind parameters in the humidex formula.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

During the summer months, residents along the coastal regions where humidity levels are high and temperatures are elevated often perceive temperatures higher than those recorded by thermometers. This phenomenon, not solely based on human psychology and senses, is referred to as perceived temperature. Briefly termed as humidex, this perceived temperature arises as a composite of parameters such as air temperature, absolute humidity, and relative humidity, significantly influencing human thermal comfort and leading to energy losses for cooling purposes in both enclosed and open spaces.

Global air temperatures have risen by 1.1°C since the world began using fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and gas, with two-thirds of this increase occurring after 1950. If current trends continue—driven by factors like population growth, fossil fuel consumption, deforestation, and desertification—the inevitable consequence will be further increases in global average temperatures. Consequently, local temperatures, including humidex values, are also on the rise across many regions. In Turkey, with its long coastal stretches and peninsula-like structure, where humidity values are relatively high, an increase in humidex is unavoidable.

Based on the analysis and evaluations conducted during the daytime hours of summer months from 1990 to 2022 across 61 stations along the Turkish coasts, the following trends were observed:

- Air temperatures have increased across all 61 stations, with a trend of 0.635°C per decade and a total increase of 2.1°C from 1990 to 2022.
- Humidex values have increased by a trend of 1.293°C per decade, resulting in a total increase of 4.3°C over 33 years.
- During summer daytime hours, humidex temperatures were calculated to range from 36-37°C, categorized as "slightly uncomfortable." Depending on physical activity and exposure duration, these conditions could lead to severe thermal stress, heat cramps, and heat exhaustion.

Regional analysis reveals that the humidex trend along the coasts of the Black Sea Region and the Marmara Region is higher compared to other coastal regions. In the Mediterranean Region and Aegean Region, many station's humidex values have exceeded

38-41°C during daytime hours, categorized as "uncomfortable" and potentially hazardous depending on exposure duration.

According to this study, conditions of thermal discomfort prevail across all Turkish coasts, with a statistically significant positive humidex trend observed at a significance level of $\alpha=0.95$. Given the anticipated increase in global air temperatures according to IPCC scenarios, humidex values along the Turkish coasts are expected to continue rising, intensifying thermal discomfort.

Considering that 75% of Turkey's population resides along the coasts, and numerous sectors including industry, tourism, and agriculture are concentrated there, the increased cooling demand due to rising humidex values will escalate energy costs. Given Turkey's energy dependence, this could inevitably trigger economic challenges. Further studies are needed to assess the influence of specific locations on the rise in humidex values. Revamping energy and climate systems, and even settlement patterns, should consider humidex values similar to other natural disasters. Calculating the effects of humidex in tourism investments and population planning can contribute to effective resource management.

It is crucial to emphasize the importance of climate change adaptation and mitigation policies. Increased humidex values in Turkey's coastal regions necessitate more effective and sustainable strategies for planning, construction, and maintenance of infrastructure projects. Increasing efforts towards structural adjustments and green infrastructure in coastal areas can help mitigate the impacts of temperature increases. Public awareness campaigns and communication strategies are essential to educate the populace about the effects of humidex and temperature increases. Educational programs should be organized to empower individuals with simple measures to enhance their thermal comfort in daily life.

Promoting energy efficiency and transitioning to sustainable energy sources are critical steps in reducing the impacts of temperature increases. Strengthening green building standards and energy efficiency policies can contribute significantly to making urbanization along coastal regions more sustainable.

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